

EDUCATION IN BAMBOO STRUCTURES: A TACTILE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Bamboo structures have been constructed in different parts of the world and, given current and future global sustainability concerns, there is a great need to expand the education in such structures at the university level. Allied to this, as a general educational observation, students show a greater interest in topics which are demonstrated physically, rather than those that are explained using the so-called ‘chalk and talk’ methods. This paper discusses the curriculum design and implementation of a tactile educational programme on bamboo structures for students in their early years of study. Examples of student work in this proposed educational programme, implemented in 2021-22 academic year at the University of Surrey, will also be presented.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo Structures; Curriculum Design; Education; Tactile Approach; Design, Assemble and Dismantle (DAD) Project

INTRODUCTION

In response to climate emergency actions to develop sustainable, carbon-sequestering materials, bamboo could be considered as an excellent alternative material for construction. In the past centuries, local communities were able to use renewable resources to create affordable and stable infrastructure, ensuring their development. In order for the next generation of architects/engineers/builders/designers to expand the applications of this fascinating grass, it is necessary to develop the education of bamboo structures at university level.

The author strongly believes in the benefits of tactile approaches in engineering education and he has been developing such educational schemes at the University of Surrey, UK, since 2014. To improve architecture/engineering students’ practical considerations of designing a sustainable structure, the Design, Assemble and Dismantle (DAD) Project was initiated. In this project, groups of participants design structures using all or part of a provided kit of prefabricated steel full-scale elements, and prepare the necessary drawings, method statement and risk assessments for construction. Each group then hands their design to another group which performs the assembly and dismantling of the structure in a limited time. Finally, each group makes a one-minute video about the experience of design, assemble and dismantle (Behnejad, 2016). Figure 1a shows a group of undergraduate students after the assembly of their structure at the University of Surrey.

Students from different universities in Brazil, China, Iran and Mexico have also taken part in the Project and exchanged their designs with Surrey students. In addition to teamwork, communication and time management skills, these international collaborations introduce more challenges such as managing language, cultural and time differences – just like the real-life situations that face international construction companies (Saleem et. al 2021). Figure 1b shows a group of undergraduate students at the University of Surrey after the assembly of a structure designed by a group of students from Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.

An additional level of complexity has been introduced into the collaboration between Surrey students and the students from the Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Occidente (ITESO), Mexico: the Mexican students have a bamboo full-scale kit instead of the steel one. Therefore, Surrey

students have to design a bamboo structure to be assembled and dismantled at ITESO, while they receive a steel design from ITESO to assemble and dismantle at Surrey, Figures 1c and 1d.

a) Surrey students in 2017

b) Designed by Ferdowsi students and assembled at Surrey, 2018

c) Designed by Surrey students and assembled at ITESO, 2019

d) Designed by ITESO students and assembled at Surrey, 2022

Figure 1: Groups of students after the assembly of their structure for the DAD Project

More recently, in addition to the lattice spatial structures in steel and bamboo, full-scale teaching kits for tensile membrane structures have also been developed. Figure 2 shows two of these kits after the assembly test at the University of Surrey.

Student evaluations show that around 90% of students have enjoyed the DAD project, felt highly engaged and were interested to participate in similar projects (Behnejad, 2016). Following the success of the project in recent years, a new curriculum was designed for the bamboo structures and implemented in the academic year 2021-22 at the University of Surrey, details of which will be discussed below.

a) Hypar membrane inside a regular tetrahedron, 2021

b) Multi-hypar membrane inside a regular octahedron, 2022

Figure 2: Full scale teaching kits for tensile membrane structures designed and fabricated at the University of Surrey for the DAD Project

EDUCATION IN BAMBOO STRUCTURES

The author has participated in several educational schemes on the design and construction of bamboo structures in the past few years. These include webinars organised by the International Network for Bamboo and Rattan (<https://www.inbar.int/event/>), 4th Bamboo in the Urban Environment Symposium organised by the University of Newcastle (<https://conferences.ncl.ac.uk/4th-bamboo-itu/>), Continuing Professional Development (CPD) course on Structural Engineering with Bamboo organised by the Institution of Structural Engineers (IStructE, 2021) and the Bamboo Online Immersion course organised by Bamboo U (Bamboo U, 2022). In addition, the author has organised a technical session on bamboo structures at the Spatial Structures Conference 2020/21 and was an instructor for a three month design to digital fabrication workshop on a bamboo structure (SpatialStructures2021, 2021). All these educational schemes are very valuable to promote bamboo structures to practitioners, however, the main aim of the present work is to discuss the introduction of a new curriculum for education in this valuable material.

The curriculum was designed as an introduction to bamboo structures for first year undergraduate students in civil and environmental engineering at the University of Surrey. It consists of four stages, namely: Introduction, Investigation, Exploration and Consolidation. The curriculum was implemented for 12 groups of 4-6 students during the second semester of 2021-22 academic year (February 2022 – May 2022). Table 1 gives an overview of the tasks and time allocated for this curriculum.

Table 1: Overview of the curriculum content

Stage	Task	Duration (hour)
Introduction	Two invited lectures	2
Investigation	Workshop 1: Identify case studies and planning	3
	Workshop 2: Tabletop model making	4
Exploration	Exhibition and group discussion	3
	Group meetings and self-study	20
	Feasibility study report preparation	15
Consolidation	Group presentation	5
	Self-reflection report	8
Total		60

Introduction

Two one-hour introductory lectures were organised for the students and delivered by invited expert speakers: Dr Martha Godina Rodriguez from Elliott Wood, UK, and Dr Nayar Gutierrez Astudillo from ITESO, Mexico. The speakers presented general information about bamboo as a construction material, its anatomy, mechanical properties, treatment and durability. Also, a number of case studies of vernacular bamboo structures, bahareque construction (a traditional building technique), connection systems and modern bamboo structures were introduced.

Investigation

This stage consisted of two workshops. The stage had the aims to further develop students' understanding about existing bamboo structures, provide examples of construction drawings, identify the main structural components, work out an appropriate scale for a tabletop model, and to become familiar with available tools and materials in a tactile manner.

In the first three-hour workshop, student groups were tasked to research modern bamboo structures and identify an existing structure, together with its construction drawings, in order to make a scaled tabletop model of it. Each group also had to prepare the list of requirements (i.e tools and materials) for model making. Figure 3a shows sample of requirements ordered by students.

The second workshop (4 hours) was dedicated to the model making, Figure 3b.

a) Sample of tools and materials ordered by students

b) Example of a tabletop bamboo model made by students

Figure 3: Student groups made a tabletop scaled model of a modern bamboo structure of their choice

Exploration

The first two tasks in this stage aimed to gain benefit from observation, and peer review and learning. The first task in this stage comprised an exhibition of the bamboo models so the whole cohort could observe and comment on all models, Figure 4. Also, each group discussed the lessons learnt from model making, challenges faced and how the bamboo models could be improved. The wide range of tabletop models helped the students to observe different techniques adopted by their peers.

Figure 4: An exhibition of the tabletop bamboo models.

In the second task, students had to explore their knowledge about bamboo structures and in a series of group meetings, develop their ideas for a specific design project in the next task.

The third task in this stage was to prepare a feasibility report for a proposed bamboo pavilion in a partner university. Each group had to choose a location at the Southwest Jiaotong University in China or ITESO in Mexico. They then prepared a report embodying the following with respect to their chosen location:

1. Background information about existing bamboo structures, including their location, appearance, functionality, capacity, etc.
2. Vision for the proposed pavilion including complementary features and potential functions.
3. Site analysis including land ownership, vegetation, ecology, topography, etc.
4. Infrastructure required for the project (e.g. road access to the site, water and energy).
5. Drawings and sketches for the bamboo pavilion. The main structural elements were to be identified, and potential applied loads should be shown on the sketches.
6. Some suggestions regarding the required foundations.

Also, in group meetings, the students could discuss their ideas and seek advice and information from the curriculum leader (the author of this paper). Examples of reports are provided in Figure 5.

Consolidation

The final stage consisted of two tasks to consolidate the knowledge and skills gained during the project. In the first task, each group had to deliver a seven-minute presentation to the rest of their cohort and the curriculum leader, discussing their proposed design and answering any questions from the audience. In the second task, each student was tasked to submit a self-reflection report assessing their group work. This could include what went well and why, what could be improved and how.

At the time of writing, the self-reflection reports from the first cohort to receive this curriculum are yet to be submitted by the students, so are not available for inclusion in this paper. However, the outcomes could be presented orally during the NOCMAT 2022.

FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

At the time of writing, a full-scale bamboo teaching kit for use in Surrey is under development to enhance the hands-on experience for the students. This would help the students to compare the workability of bamboo with the steel structure currently available for the DAD Project, in practical terms.

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